

CHARACTER TRAITS AND BEHAVIOR OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7793624>

Annotation: the correct upbringing of the character of young people is one of the Central and important tasks of raising a harmonious generation. Experts confirm that the first appearance of behavior can be seen since childhood, before school.

Keywords: youth, destructive behavior, character, student, activity, harmonious generation, upbringing, type, personality.

Currently, one of the issues of relevance and consideration is the educational activity, behavior, character traits of students and young people, their exemplary behavior in society. And this requires research and analysis. We know that fundamental reforms in the educational system, great changes in the minds of people depend on the potential, personal qualities and position of students studying in the higher education system, which, to say, will never be an exaggeration.

Character education is one of the Central and important tasks of raising a harmonious generation. Experts confirm that the first appearance of behavior can be seen since childhood, before school. In the process of growth, new qualities and characteristics appear, the personality is formed. To educate a strong and brave person, it is necessary to train him in team games with clear rules and plots, to form responsibility, from childhood, first solve simple tasks, and then move on to complex ones, observe discipline and calm, evaluate the result and make comments.

Character traits such as caring, kindness, politeness or, conversely, anger, selfishness, indifference arise precisely from childhood. In adolescence, volitional qualities, behavior and worldview are formed. The formation of intellectual, emotional and volitional characteristics of a character, such as assertiveness, critical view, Understanding, provocation, sympathy, cheerfulness, mechribony, is also formed in the same way. And then the characteristic features change in New conditions, depending on the existing conditions. In adulthood, the change of character becomes stable and acquires a certain shape. Over the years, personality character traits also develop, changing in accordance with age. In particular, the leading activity of the student is reading. The activity of study affects the development of the characteristics of the student's psychic processes, the acquisition of professionally important signs, skills and qualifications. If reading becomes creativity, it also positively affects students ' worldview in the emotional sphere, cultivates attention and memory, creates a sense of satisfaction. Alternatively, interest in the process of cognition increases.

A huge number of character traits are considered deep and active inclinations that determine a person's work-actions, in these inclinations the motivational power of character traits is manifested, and due to strength, often act contrary to objective conditions and apply completely non-objective methods of action. Some people knowingly choose a difficult task,

some on the contrary. When character traits encourage acting in a certain way, and sometimes in contrast to circumstances, they become better namochim in difficult moments. The personality character is tested in the struggle with the opposing conditions. Due to the fact that character traits are the characteristics of an individual that are difficult to form and strengthen, the physiological basis of a character also consists of the changed characteristics of the nervous system in the process of individual delusions.

During study, in general, in life, each individual (student) who does not realize himself can sometimes form negative characteristic features in his character and create conditions in which these features prevail. The result is the formation of destructive behavior in the character of the individual. The formation of destructive behavior in an individual character has been studied by a number of psychologist scientists. In Particular, E.Krechmer, U.Sheldon, K.G.Yung, Yu.M.Lotman, E.A.Lichko, and others have researched causes and ways to eliminate destructive behavior formation.

Destructive behavior can range from mild to strong. In terms of destructive behavior, a person differs according to his psychological description. In particular, a person of the distim type, on the contrary, has difficulty getting into camgap, communication, is a pessimist, withdraws himself from conflicts, likes to be alone at home. Those of the cycloid type tend to change their mood quickly, at a good time-hypertim, at a bad time-the dysthymic type. The lamentable type, on the other hand, is passive in communication, verbal and nonverbal reactions are sluggish, stubborn, sometimes belligerent, often in various conflict, the initiator of thenint. Those of the reinforcing type are camgap, like to teach Intelligence, want to achieve high results, are impactful, vindictive doubters. They tend to enlarge, exaggerate small-small problems. The emotive type likes to engage in communication with a narrow circle of people, tries not to notice from the outside when offended, feels kind, caring, responsible. Rejoices in the achievements of others.

Representatives of the demonstrative (demonstrative) type quickly enter into communication, strive for leadership, like authority and praise, are able to attract others, have unique thinking, behavior.

Each of the above-mentioned destructive behavior personality types has its own aspects. Due to this, character traits and personality destructiveness are from areas that require learning. Famous psychoanalysts Sigmund Freud and Erich Fromm interpreted the essence of desruction in different ways. Sigmund Freud believed that he was distinguished by the fact that he was absorbed and guided by all personalities. Fromm, on the other hand, believed that perversion sometimes occurs in all people. If it appeared, then he argued that it would be directed to the inner world of the individual and only then to the outside (as a projection). Of course, in the properly organized educational process, it is possible to educate and correct the accentuation of character. Only specialists in this regard should develop the necessary programs and introduce them into practice.

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